

Synthesis of Oxygenated 3-*p*-Benzoquinonyl- and 3-Aryl-4-hydroxycoumarins

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A synthesis of 4,5-dihydroxy-3-*p*-benzoquinonylcoumarin is described involving condensation of 4,5-dihydroxycoumarin with *p*-benzoquinone. Subsequent Thiele's acetylation/reductive acetylation offered acetoxy-3-aryl-4-acetoxycoumarin which on hydrolysis gave the corresponding hydroxylated 3-aryl-4-hydroxycoumarins. The structures of these products have been established by spectral data. Antibacterial and antifungal activities of these compounds are discussed.

THE occurrence of 3-aryl-4-hydroxycoumarins in plants, namely, robustic acid^{1,2} extracted from roots of *Derris robusta*, scandenin and lonchocarpic acid³ from *Derris scandens* have biogenetic significance as these co-occur with isoflavones. All these naturally occurring 3-arylcoumarins have a hydroxyl in 4-position and none of these have been synthesised so far probably because the intermediates required for their synthesis are not easily available by the methods known at present. The present communication therefore deals with the facile synthesis of 3-*p*-benzoquinonyl-4-hydroxycoumarins which on subsequent Thiele's acetylation/reductive acetylation and final hydrolysis offered oxygenated 3-aryl-4-hydroxycoumarins. There are six general methods⁴⁻⁹ available for synthesis of 3-aryl-4-hydroxycoumarins. The method due to Wagh and Usgaonkar involved condensation of 4-hydroxycoumarin and *p*-benzoquinone in acetone giving rise to 3-*p*-benzoquinonyl-4-hydroxycoumarin which was finally converted to 4-hydroxy-3-arylcoumarin in good yield.

In the present investigation, this method has been extended to polyhydroxycoumarins and the products formed have been characterised on the basis of spectral data. It was also observed that in these cases also the condensation took place only at 3-position of coumarin and not in the parent oxygenated phenyl ring giving rise to oxygenated 3-arylcoumarins in good yield.

As a representative case, 4,5-dihydroxycoumarin (0.01 mol) was condensed with *p*-benzoquinone (0.02 mol) in aqueous acetone. The contents were stirred for 4 h at room temperature. The solution slowly turned dark brown and a yellow compound separated out. The compound (m.p. 230°, M^+ 284, single spot tlc C_6H_6 -EtOAc 1 : 1) was soluble in 5% sodium hydroxide solution indicating the presence of free 4-hydroxyl group. It gave pink colour with concentrated H_2SO_4 and sodium hydroxide solution. In addition, the compound underwent

Thiele's acetylation with acetic anhydride/concentrated H_2SO_4 and reductive acetylation with acetic anhydride/pyridine/zinc dust, indicating the presence of quinonoid system in its structure. In the ir spectra, quinonoid compound (1) showed absorptions at 3 300 (OH), 1 690 (coumarin C=O) and 1 660 cm^{-1} (quinone C=O). The compound 1 exhibited in uv. absorption maxima at 215 nm ($\log \epsilon$ 4.40), 275 (4.17) and 315 (4.07). The above spectral data is in agreement with the reported spectra of quinones^{10,11}. The pmr spectrum (DMSO) indicated signals at δ 5.4–5.8 (3H, m, quinone protons) and 6.8–7.0 (3H, m, aromatic protons). On the basis of the above chemical and spectral data, compound 1 has been assigned 4,5-dihydroxy-3-(*p*-benzoquinonyl)coumarin structure (Chart 1). The mass spectrum indicated M^+ at 284 and other ions at m/z 177, 136, 108 and 107.

On Thiele's, acetylation, the quinonoid compound (1) offered colourless pentaacetate (2, R=Ac; m.p. 200°, M^+ 512, tlc single spot, insoluble in sodium bicarbonate solution and -ve ferric chloride test). The ir spectra showed absorptions at 1 750, 1 710 (ester C=O) and 1 660 cm^{-1} (coumarin C=O). The pmr spectrum of pentaacetate in TFA indicated three signals at δ 2.13 (6H), 2.34 (3H) and 2.52 (6H) assigned for five acetate groups. The aromatic

protons appeared as multiplet at δ 7.26–7.4 (5H). In the mass spectrum, the other ions were present at m/z 484, 302, 284 and 266.

The structure of pentaacetate has been assigned as 4,5-diacetoxy-3-(2',4',5'-triacetoxyphenyl)coumarin (2) and the other possible structures have been ruled out on the basis of cyclisation of 2 (R=Ac) with methanolic hydrogen chloride to 1,8,9-trihydroxycoumestan (6) which has also been prepared by Wanzlick's method^{1,2} and found identical in all respects (ir superimposable) (Chart 2). Further, the quinonoid compound (1) on reductive acetylation with Ac₂O/pyridine/zinc dust offered colourless tetraacetate (m.p. 252°, insoluble in 5% sodium

Chart 2

bicarbonate solution and -ve FeCl₃ test). The ir spectra of the compound exhibited two absorptions at 1 750, 1 720 (ester C=O) and 1 660 cm⁻¹ (coumarin C=O). On the basis of the above chemical and spectral data, the tetraacetate has been assigned 4,5-diacetoxy-3-(2',5'-diacetoxyphenyl)coumarin (4, R=Ac) structure. Compounds 2 and 4 were hydrolysed with methanolic hydrochloric acid to form 4,5-dihydroxy-3-(2',4',5'-trihydroxyphenyl)coumarin (3, R=H) and 4,5-dihydroxy-3-(2',5'-dihydroxyphenyl)coumarin (4, R=H), respectively. The compound 3 showed ir bands at 3 320 (OH) and 1 680 cm⁻¹ (coumarin C=O). The uv spectra indicated absorption maxima at 220 nm (log ϵ 4.43) 270 (3.97) and 312 (4.02).

Similarly, compound 4 exhibited two strong bands at 3 200 (OH) and 1 650 cm⁻¹ (coumarin C=O). Three absorption maxima in uv were present at 218 nm (log ϵ 4.40), 275 (3.99) and 315 (4.05).

Adopting the above procedure, the following 4-hydroxy-3-*p*-benzoquinonylcoumarins were prepared, namely, 4,6-dihydroxy-3-*p*-benzoquinonylcoumarin, 4,7-dihydroxy-3-*p*-benzoquinonylcoumarin and 4,5,7-trihydroxy-3-*p*-benzoquinonylcoumarin (Table 1). In all these cases, the yield of the final product is uniformly good (45–65%). On Thiele's acetylation, the above 4-hydroxy-3-quinonylcoumarin offered the corresponding pentaacetates, which were subsequently hydrolysed by methanolic hydrochloric acid to the following coumarins, namely, 4,6-dihydroxy-3-(2',4',5'-trihydroxyphenyl)coumarin, 4,7-dihydroxy-3-(2',4',5'-trihydroxyphenyl)coumarin, 4,5,7-trihydroxy-3-(2',4',5'-trihydroxyphenyl)coumarin, respectively (Table 2). On reductive acetylation, the above 3-*p*-benzoquinonylcoumarins offered the corresponding tetraacetates, which were hydrolysed subsequently to the corresponding hydroxylated coumarins, namely, 4,6-dihydroxy-3-(2',5'-dihydroxyphenyl)coumarin, 4,7-dihydroxy-3-(2',5'-dihydroxyphenyl)coumarin, 4,5,7-trihydroxy-3-(2',5'-dihydroxyphenyl)coumarin in good yield (60–68%) (Table 3).

All the compounds described above have been tested for antibacterial (by tube dilution method) and antifungal (by plate method) activity. The compounds, namely, 4,5-dihydroxy-3-*p*-benzoquinonylcoumarin, 4,6-dihydroxy-3-*p*-benzoquinonylcoumarin, 4,5,7-trihydroxy-3-*p*-benzoquinonylcoumarin were found active at 100 ppm against *Staphylococcus aureus* and *E. coli*. However, these compounds were not active against *Aspergillus niger* even at 100 ppm.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL, PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF 4-HYDROXY-3-(*p*-BENZOQUINONYL)COUMARINS

Sl. no.	R	M.p. °C	Yield %	Mol. formula	Analysis % : Found/Calcd.)		λ_{max} nm	(log ϵ)	ν_{OH} cm ⁻¹	ν_{CO} cm ⁻¹
					C	H				
1.	5-Hydroxy	230	58	C ₁₈ H ₈ O ₆	63.40 (63.38)	2.79 (2.80)	215 275 315	(4.40) (4.17) (4.07)	3 300	1 690 1 660
2.	6-Hydroxy	253	67	C ₁₈ H ₈ O ₆	63.40 (63.38)	2.79 (2.80)	218 280 310	(4.37) (4.11) (4.05)	3 300	1 680 1 640
3.	7-Hydroxy	246	54	C ₁₈ H ₈ O ₆	63.36 (63.38)	2.79 (2.80)	213 283 315	(4.39) (4.12) (4.06)	3 350	1 680 1.660
4.	5,7-Dihydroxy	264	47	C ₁₈ H ₈ O ₇	59.8 (60.0)	2.67 (2.66)	215 280 310	(4.38) (4.13) (4.05)	3 350	1 690 1 665

TABLE 2—ANALYTICAL, PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF 4-HYDROXY-3-(2', 4', 5'-TRIHYDROXYPHENYL)COUMARIN AND THEIR ACETATES

Sl. no	R, R'	M.p. °C	Yield %	Mol. formula	Analysis % · Found/(Calcd.)		λ_{max}	(log ϵ)	ν_{OH} cm ⁻¹	$\nu_{C=O}$ cm ⁻¹
					C	H				
1.	R = H, R' = 5-OH	272	66	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ O ₇	59.50 (59.60)	3.33 (3.31)	220 270 312	(4.43) (3.97) (4.02)	3320	1680
2.	R = Ac, R' = 5-OAc	230	78	C ₂₅ H ₂₀ O ₁₁	58.60 (58.59)	3.99 (3.90)	-	-	-	1660 1750 1710
3.	R = H, R' = 6-OH	250	63	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ O ₇	59.61 (59.60)	3.30 (3.31)	222 270 312	(4.41) (3.92) (4.07)	3300	1690
4.	R = Ac, R' = 6-OAc	162	61	C ₂₅ H ₂₀ O ₁₁	58.60 (58.59)	3.98 (3.90)	-	-	-	1640 1740 1710
5.	R = H, R' = 7-OH	276	70	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ O ₇	59.62 (59.60)	3.33 (3.31)	218 280 305	(4.42) (3.90) (3.99)	3350	1685
6.	R = Ac, R' = 7-OAc	260	72	C ₂₅ H ₂₀ O ₁₁	58.58 (58.59)	3.87 (3.90)	-	-	-	1660 1750 1710
7.	R = H, R' = 5,7-diOH	278	57	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ O ₈	56.59 (56.60)	3.12 (3.14)	225 275 310	(4.40) (3.89) (4.03)	3315	1680
8.	R = Ac, R' = 5,7-diOAc	259	60	C ₂₇ H ₂₂ O ₁₄	56.85 (56.84)	3.87 (3.85)	-	-	-	1650 1740 1720

Experimental

General procedure :

4,5-Dihydroxy-3-p-benzoquinonylcoumarin (1) : 4,5-Dihydroxycoumarin (1.8 g, 0.01 mol) and *p*-benzoquinone (2.16 g, 0.02 mol) were dissolved in aqueous acetone (30 ml, 1 : 1) and stirred for 4 h at room temperature and the solution turned dark brown. The separated yellow solid was filtered, washed with aqueous acetone, dried and recrystallised from ethanol as light yellow crystals (1.65 g, 58%), m.p. 230° (Found : C, 63.40 ; H, 2.79. C₁₅H₈O₆ requires : C, 63.38 ; H, 2.80%).

4,5-Diacetoxy-3-(2',4',5'-triacetoxyphenyl)coumarin (2) : To the suspension of 4,5-dihydroxy-3-*p*-benzoquinonylcoumarin (1 ; 1.5 g) in Ac₂O (8 ml) was added two drops of concentrated sulphuric acid. The contents were kept aside for 3 h and then poured over crushed ice. The colourless precipitate of 2 formed was filtered, dried and recrystallised from ethyl acetate as colourless crystals (2 g, 78%), m.p. 200° (Found : C, 58.60 ; H, 3.99. C₂₅H₂₀O₁₁ requires : C, 58.59 ; H, 3.97%).

4,5-Diacetoxy-3-(2',5'-diacetoxyphenyl)coumarin (4) : Compound 1 (1.5 g) was treated with Ac₂O (10 ml), pyridine (3 drops) and zinc dust (1 g). The hot mixture was refluxed on a water-bath for 4 h and the contents were poured later over crushed ice. The light brownish crystalline tetraacetate (4) that slowly separated out was filtered, dried and recrystallised from ethyl acetate as colourless crystals (1.5 g, 66%), m.p. 252° (Found : C, 60.80 ; H, 3.98. C₂₅H₁₈O₁₀ requires : C, 60.79 ; H, 3.96%).

Deacetylation procedure : Compound 2 (1.13 g) was dissolved in (1 : 1) methanol/hydrochloric acid (10 ml, 1 : 1) and refluxed on a water-bath for 1 h. The contents were transferred to ice-cold water in a beaker. A yellow precipitate (3, R=OH) that separated out was filtered, dried and recrystallised from methanol as light yellow crystals (0.40 g, 66%), m.p. 272° (Found : C, 59.5 ; H, 3.33. C₁₅H₁₀O₇ requires : C, 59.6 ; H, 3.31%).

1,8,9-Trihydroxycoumestan (6) : Compound 2 (2.3 g) was dissolved in methanol and dry hydrogen chloride gas was passed for 2 h. Later the reaction

TABLE 3—ANALYTICAL, PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF 4-HYDROXY-3-(2,5'-DIHYDROXYPHENYL)COUMARIN AND THEIR ACETATES

Sl. no.	R, R'	M.p. °C	Yield %	Mol. formula	Analysis % : Found (Calcd.)		λ_{max} (log ϵ)	ν_{OH} cm ⁻¹	$\nu_{C=O}$ cm ⁻¹
					C	H			
1.	R = H, R' = 5-OH	280	59	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ O ₆	62.94 (62.93)	3.51 (3.49)	218 (4.40) 275 (3.99) 315 (4.05)	3 200	1 650
2.	R = Ac, R' = 5-OAc	252	66	C ₂₁ H ₁₆ O ₁₀	60.80 (60.79)	3.98 (3.96)	-	-	1 660 1 740 1 720
3.	R = H, R' = 6-OH	264	57	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ O ₆	62.95 (62.93)	3.50 (3.49)	225 (4.39) 275 (3.96) 310 (4.08)	3 250	1 650
4.	R = Ac, R' = 6-OAc	258	64	C ₂₁ H ₁₆ O ₁₀	60.80 (60.79)	3.97 (3.96)	-	-	1 670 1 740 1 720
5.	R = H, R' = 7-OH	270	62	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ O ₆	62.91 (62.93)	3.49 (3.49)	223 (4.40) 275 (4.00) 310 (4.06)	3 200	1 650
6.	R = Ac, R' = 7-OAc	260	67	C ₂₁ H ₁₆ O ₁₀	60.81 (60.79)	3.98 (3.96)	-	-	1 640 1 730 1 700
7.	R = H, R' = 5,7-diOH	269	68	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ O ₇	59.58 (59.60)	3.32 (3.31)	220 (4.49) 272 (3.90) 305 (4.08)	3 300	1 640
8.	R = Ac, R' = 5,7-diOAc	260	65	C ₂₁ H ₁₆ O ₁₁	58.58 (58.59)	4.00 (3.90)	-	-	1 670 1 740 1 710

mixture was refluxed on a water-bath for 8 h. The light brownish coloured compound that separated out was filtered, dried and recrystallised from excess acetone (0.83 g, 60%), m.p. >300° (Found: C, 63.36; H, 2.80. C₁₅H₈O₆ requires: C, 63.38; H, 2.81%).

Alternate procedure: To a solution of 4,5-dihydroxycoumarin (1.78 g) and catechol (1.1 g) in aqueous acetone was added sodium acetate (9.0 g). A solution of potassium ferricyanide (9.0 g) in water (20 ml) was added to the above solution dropwise while stirring. During the process of addition (0.5 h) brownish crystals that separated out were filtered, washed with water, dried and recrystallised from excess acetone, m.p. >300° (ir superimposable with 6).

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